

Research of systems for providing electronic document management in higher education institutions

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Abstract

The publication provides a thorough and detailed analysis of the methods of electronic document management systems and algorithms for data processing and documentation management. The article reveals in detail the topic of the effectiveness of the use of EDMS, as well as the automation of business processes of enterprises. As a result of the research, a system based on the use of algorithms of data processing and document management systems was proposed and developed, which will help automate business processes in educational institutions and increase the level of efficiency of the educational process for both teachers and students.

Keywords

Document management, Electronic Document, Electronic Document Management, Document management, Machine-readable document, Electronic Document Management System, Electronic Signature.

1. Introduction

A rapidly evolving technology, the Electronic Document Management System (EDMS), is seen as a potential answer for businesses in need of efficient information management. Applications for EDMS are designed to manage electronic documents at every stage of their existence, from creation through archiving. Document generation, storage, and retrieval, administration, version control, workflow, and several distribution formats are among its features.

As described in the article by Joseph P. Sathiadass and G.N. Wikramanayake, "Methods and technologies of document management"[1], document management is a collection of components rather than a single thing or piece of technology. This involves the use of technology that enables interaction together with a variety of people and information in a business process. The technologies that make up the EDMS are separated into many functional categories. We introduce them and discuss the techniques for managing electronic documents in this post. We also look into the EDMS market's near future and come to the conclusion that it is at a crossroads in its own life cycle and is made up of a highly fragmented set of products without a single integrated provider or platform for automating the complete document lifecycle from start to finish.

Most organizations have a huge amount of information needed for their current projects or for their future projects in the form of knowledge of their employees or in documents. But the lack of information exchange between people and various project groups, the lack of proper management of information resources and the lack of support from knowledge workers make this information inaccessible and

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useless. Consequently, there was a need for a system that could meet this requirement and solve these problems.

The Electronic Document Management System (EDMS) solves most of these problems and is considered as a solution for organizations that need a solution for effective information management. According to an article published on the international information agency “kazinform” dated October 7, 2014 [2], the “Unified Electronic Document Management System” (UEDMS), which was introduced in 2006 in order to improve the efficiency and quality of managerial decision-making, allowed to structure document databases, reduce the time for providing a response, creating a request and ensured transparency the effectiveness of managers' activities. “Currently, the UEDMS is used in 93 central and 1711 territorial state bodies,” the Ministry of Investment and Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan cites data. Although data management has been around for about 30 years or so, document management only appeared about 10 years ago. EDMS became popular with the advent of technology and computers.

There is a need to create a system that provides electronic document management in universities. To facilitate the process of forming personal documentation of teaching staff and automating the learning process among students. Also, the study of electronic document management systems to improve the efficiency of business processes in the activities of universities.

2. Modern methods and technologies of electronic document management systems

Applications for EDMS are designed to manage electronic documents at every stage of their existence, from creation through archiving. Document generation, storage, and retrieval, administration, version control, workflow, and a variety of distribution formats are among its features.

- Document Creation: A document is a container that combines information from various sources in several formats on a specific topic to meet the needs of a particular person or organization.
- Storage and retrieval: This includes storing and retrieving documents on a storage device such as a hard drive, magnetic tape, etc.
- Management: This covers a wide area of effective management of all documents to meet the needs of the organization and individuals.
- Version control: This is a way to track changes made to a document and the ability to extract old versions of the document.
- Workflow: This is a way to track the status of the document and who is responsible for this step.
- Multiple delivery formats: Ways to deliver document content in various formats, such as PDF, Word, images, according to the requirements of end users.

Basic principles of electronic document management:

- One-time registration of the document, which allows you to uniquely identify the document.
- The possibility of parallel execution of operations, which allows to reduce the time of movement of documents and increase the efficiency of their execution
- The continuity of the document movement, which allows identifying the person responsible for the execution of the document (task) at each moment in the life of the document (process).
- A single (or coordinated distributed) database of document information, which makes it possible to eliminate the possibility of duplication of documents.
- An efficiently organized document search system that allows you to find a document with minimal information about it.

- A developed system of reporting on various statuses and attributes of documents, which allows you to control the movement of documents through document management processes and make management decisions based on data from reports.

Document management is not a single technology, but rather a combination of elements. This is the use of information and various users in a business process combined with technology that allows interaction. Thus, the Document Management Space can be divided into four main areas, namely: documents, people, processes and technologies.

Documents: The wealth of an organization is the information it has. Approximately 20% of this information is contained in the form of data, and the remaining 80% is in documents. 20% of the data is usually well managed and stored in databases. A lot of effort has been spent on managing and using this data, without paying much attention to the documents containing most of the information.

People: Like any other systems, the document management system also serves many different users. Users can be Creators, Coordinators, or Consumers. One person can also play multiple roles. The creator is the author and generates the contents of the document. The coordinators ensure that the document is properly reviewed and approved for publication. They are responsible for allocating tasks for other participants to perform on the document. They are responsible for delivering the document to the Consumer. Consumers are the real end users of documents who read or study them. Consumers rely on a Coordinator to deliver them what they want in the appropriate format.

Processes: When a document goes from concept to consumption, a process must be established to ensure that everything goes according to plan and in accordance with expectations. Figure 1 shows the process of converting data into Knowledge.

Figure 1: Process of converting data

Technology: With the rapid development of technology, a powerful computer with a graphical interface has become commonplace in most offices. Image creation, databases, networking, and desktop applications are some examples of technologies related to a document management system.

The technologies that make up the EDMS can be divided into several different functional groups, namely:

Conversion: Most documents consist of text, images, and multimedia objects. Since each of these formats is fundamentally different, they must be converted using different tools and methods. Conversion is usually considered as a process that does not bring added value. But conversion, which helps improve search and retrieval performance, is seen as a value-adding process.

Some of the common standard formats are:

Text – ASCII, SGML, HTML

Graphics – CGM, IGES, TIFF, GIF, JPEG

Multimedia – MPEG

The document conversion process is described in Figure 2. Here, the source format is the format of the source documents, and the target format is the format required/preferred by end users. A filter is used in the middle to find the best way to perform this conversion.

Figure 2: Document conversion

Indexing: With the growing number of document repositories and online document sets, the speed of information retrieval becomes critical. Indexing allows you to do this by splitting the document into more detailed parts down to the word level. Inversion of terms is one of the popular ways of indexing. This method will have a sorted list of all the keywords in the file with pointers pointing to the actual location. Usually, documents are initially transferred to the indexing process. Some of the most popular indexing systems, such as Open Text, Verity, Fulcrum, can accept most basic text documents.

Search: Any EDMS should provide the user with the ability to search. The user should be able to search for a specific document or a document containing certain information without delay. The effectiveness of information retrieval is measured by feedback and accuracy. Recall is the proportion of relative extracted materials, and accuracy is the proportion of extracted materials that are relevant.

3. Use and efficiency of electronic document management systems in business process automation

As stated in the article from Maslov, A.V., “The role of the electronic document management system in the automation of business processes” [3], the business process in the company's activities is a system of consistent, purposeful and regulated activities that achieve results that are significant for the organization. The introduction of EDMS allows all time-consuming data processing procedures to be carried out automatically, which greatly simplifies the work of performers. The system can automate the following processes:

Registration of documents: all incoming correspondence is registered in the system, taking into account its purpose and type. After receiving the registration number, the document goes into operation. With the help of the functionality, the system generates control cards, which can be used to track the progress of the execution of the document, indicating the deadlines and performers. To simplify the search, all documents receive their own barcodes. An electronic digital analogue is replacing the usual signature.

Assignment of orders: the automatic system provides for the creation of a draft resolution on any document that specifies the performers. After that, the documents are automatically sent to specific performers. At the same time, the executors can unsubscribe the assigned documents to the lower level with automatic accounting of all the resulting branches. The management has access to the whole picture of assignments, as well as to reports on the implementation of documents.

Organization of document execution control: control over the execution of documents is carried out automatically. In the system, it is possible to set control dates for each document in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Sending notifications from the accounting card and setting reminders about the need to return to work with the document helps to avoid a situation when the contractor, due to forgetfulness, does not have time to finish the work on time. For higher-level structures, various reports are generated for a certain period.

Document search: simplification of the search for the necessary documents is achieved by a set of details for each document for which the selection is carried out. The most frequently used search queries

are remembered by the system, which offers access to them to the direct executor. There is also a contextual search with further printing or saving in various office formats.

Administration: all user actions are automatically recorded in logs. The user is provided with his access rights, which are assigned by the system administrator during registration according to the structure of the enterprise. At the same time, the user can independently configure the settings of his desktop and personal folders.

In the current competitive environment, the winner is often not the one who makes the best product, but the one who can work faster and manages to capture the market. An employee who works with documents spends about one hour searching for the necessary data. From which we can conclude that approximately 2.5 days are obtained in a month. If we take into account all the costs per employee, then the use of an automated document management system will give an excellent reserve for saving the company's funds.

4. Electronic document management systems in educational institutions of Kazakhstan

The article from Sokolov E.A. and Sereda S.N. "Electronic document management of the university" [4] discusses the implementation of electronic document management systems in educational institutions. The analysis of the subject area of the offer of ready-made software products is carried out. A variant of solving the problem of organizing electronic document management as an information service in the automated information system of the university is given.

Effective management of an organization in an information society is largely determined by the development of the corporate information infrastructure in general and the perfection of the enterprise's document management system in particular. The transition from paper to electronic document management is one of the urgent priorities of automation. The promptness of access, security and relevance of information about the company's activities necessary for decision-making on the part of management are the necessary requirements for electronic document management systems (EDMS).

1. There are four approaches to the automation of the university 's document flow:
2. Purchase of a ready-made EDMS. To date, several dozen different systems are offered on the market, differing in functionality, cost and technical solutions.
3. Implementation of an electronic document management subsystem as part of the purchase of a corporate information system, or its add-on.
4. Development of own EDMS optimized for the structure and features of each specific enterprise.
5. Rent of information services (document storage, software tools for working with documents, etc.) on the Internet based on outsourcing and cloud technologies.

Each of the approaches has its own advantages and disadvantages. So, when purchasing an autonomous system, you should take into account possible additional costs for optimization and modernization of the organization, technical support and client licenses.

To compare the EDMS presented on the market of Kazakhstan, the most popular systems were selected by the number of implementations: 1C: (Russia), E1 Euphrates (Russia), Documentolog (Kazakhstan), ESEDO (Kazakhstan), TENGRIDOK (Kazakhstan), ARTA SYNERGY (Kazakhstan), Docsvision EDMS (Russia), DIRECTUM (Russia). Table 1 shows a detailed analysis of the various functionality of each system, such as localization capabilities, integration with other systems, support for local software, etc.

Table 1

Analysis of systems

Functional requirement	1C: Document management	E1 Euphrates	Docu mentolog	ES ED O	TENGRI DOCK	ARTA SYNERGY	Docs-vision	DIREC TUM
Availability of a full-featured web interface for the user's workplaces	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-
Administrator	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-
Multilingual interface: Russian	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
English	+	-	-	-	+	?	+	?
Kazakh	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-
The possibility of localization	+	?	+	+	+	+	+	+
Integration with SharePoint	?	+	-	-	+	-	+	-
Integration with other systems	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	+

According to the resolution published on the official information resource of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated October 31, 2018, No. 703 "On approval of the Rules of documentation, documentation management and use of electronic document management systems in state and non-state organizations" [5], in state organizations, the specifics of documentation, documentation management and use of electronic document management systems will be determined by the administration. In accordance with this resolution, a general form and a general template for filling out documentation will be developed, as well as algorithms for electronic document management systems for various government organizations, including universities.

According to an article published on the international news agency "sputnik" dated April 8, 2022 [6], the Ministry of Education and Science recommends that universities not create their own paper types of reporting but switch to a digital version of document management. The Ministry of Education and Science has reduced the list of documents for the reporting of Kazakhstani universities. A number of documents for reporting universities have been reduced:

- the statement of accounting of teaching hours of work of teachers for each month;
- a statement of teachers' study time for the year;
- examination sheet;
- minutes of the meetings of the commissions for the final certification of students. Minutes of the meeting of the commission for the final certification of students on passing the final certification exams;
- minutes of the meeting of the commission for the final certification of students on the assignment of qualifications;
- minutes of the meeting of the commission for the final certification of the student's final work;
- examination sheet;
- the work plan of the department.

Electronic document management systems in its high-quality execution, using modern methods of processing various data and documentation management algorithms can automate business processes.

5. Development of edms for higher educational institutions on the example of IITU

When starting to create an electronic document management system, you need to determine the functionality of the system itself. Make those. the task takes into account all the features of the enterprise. Choose the optimal method and the appropriate algorithm for processing the necessary data and managing all documentation. After determining the technical part, it is necessary to develop a design concept and the name of the system. The system being developed is called "OnayDOCs", which literally translates as "Documents Easily" or "Easy Documents", which fully conveys the essence of the system. The design concept consists of the following parts:

Wireframe – A website wireframe, also known as a page outline or screen plan, is a visual guide that represents a website wireframe. The term wireframe is taken from other fields in which a wireframe is used to represent a three-dimensional shape and volume (fig. 3,4).

Figure 3: Wireframe of system

Figure 4: Wireframe of system

Mockup – this is a product layout with a design solution placed on it. Using mockup, you can see the product "in action". Mock-up can be both electronic and physical. The electronic version of the layouts is used to demonstrate products (fig. 5,6)

Figure 5: Mockup of system

Figure 6: Mockup of system

When creating a demonstration material, not just a picture is created, but a three-dimensional image, which brings the electronic layout even closer to realism.

As described in the article from Johnny Levanier, "4 techniques for creating mockups" [7], describes 4 techniques for creating layouts for more efficient use. Having made a comparative analysis, it was decided to use a more suitable technique. for use in the project.

All data of each user will be linked to the database of the organization system. On the example of IITU, these are dl.iitu and platonus. It will be possible to log in from the account of both the teacher and the student, Figure 7, 8. Depending on which one or another functionality of the system will be available. In the profile where all the data necessary for full-fledged work in the system is available. For teachers: Department, position, degree, scientific articles, etc. and for students as: course of study, group, Dean's office, disciplines, etc.

Figure 7: Authorization page

Figure 8: Authorization page

The menu is a specific list of sections of the site, clicking on which the user navigates to them. In other words, this is a list of links to the categories of the site. Figure 9.

The main functionality of the automated system will be available in the main menu. Where the formation and monitoring of personal documentation of teaching staff on the basis of the university department will be available. Automated and systematized electronic document flow between various departments of organizations (university). Downloading ready-made document templates for each user to facilitate the learning process.

Figure 9: Main page

6. Conclusion

Automation of document flow as a direction of office work is a consequence of the growing number of official documentations accompanying the activities of any company. The automation system or electronic document management system (EDMS) provides support for management processes, allows you to automate work with documents. Its objects are not only electronic and paper documents, but also business processes reflected in their movement.

Research of the latest methods in the generation and control of electronic documents and their use in an automated electronic document management system will help to optimize the educational process.

Electronic document management systems in its high-quality execution, using modern methods of processing various data and documentation management algorithms can automate business processes and improve the efficiency of universities.

OnayDOC is an automated system designed for storing and creating electronic documents of the organization, forming and monitoring personal documentation of the teaching staff. The system will help to establish document flow between all departments of the university, speed up the process of obtaining documents, eliminate problems such as queues of students in front of each department, the need to fill in manually, which will increase efficiency and facilitate the learning process.

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